

A Example of growth rate sinusoid**B**

parameter	value
Growth rate amplitude ($\mu\text{m/d}$)	20
Growth rate period (days)	365
Growth rate phase (day of year)	100
Growth rate average ($\mu\text{m/d}$)	15
Growth rate skew (0 – 100)	70